

The background of the cover features an aerial photograph of a river winding through a dry, brown landscape. The river is a vibrant blue-green color. In the bottom right corner, there is a dark blue area with a white line graph showing an upward trend, overlaid on a grid of white lines.

International Scientific and Practical Conference

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

PROCEEDINGS
(Conference Proceedings)

May 19, 2026

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

WICAR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO
WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT
IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT
OF CLIMATE CHANGE**

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

May 19, 2026
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

INTERNATIONAL PROGRAM COMMITTEE

Chairman:

Umarov A.A. First Vice-Rector for Academic Affairs, UWED

Vice Chairman

Dadabaev T. Vice-Rector for Research and Innovation, UWED

Deputy Chairs:

Raimova G. M. Professor, Head of Department, UWED

Rasulov A. S. Professor, UWED

Seytov A.J. Professor, UWED.

Program Committee Members:

Rasulov A. S. Professor, UWED

Seytov A.J. Professor, UWED.

Dalabaev U. Professor, UWED

Umarova Sh. Dotsent, UWED

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Chairman:

Djalalov M.M. Vice-Rector for Digital Transformation and Economy, UWED

Deputy Chairs:

Raimova G. M. Head of the Department of System Analysis and Mathematical Modelling, UWED

Seytov A.J. Professor, UWED.

Organizing Committee Members:

Abdullaev E.E. (Dean, UWED, Uzbekistan)

Dalabaev U. (UWED, Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova M. (UWED, Uzbekistan)

Umarova Sh. (UWED, Uzbekistan)

CONFERENCE SECRETARIAT

Umarova Sh.G. (Head of the Secretariat), Buriev A., Kasimova N.J., Maraimova K. Sh., Khasanova D.R., Yarashev I., Solaeva M., Mustafakulova A. Kh., Akabirkhodjaeva D.R.

International Scientific and Practical Conference -2026

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference innovative approaches to water resource management in arid regions in the context of climate change on May 19, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The conference aims to discuss key issues of effective water resource management in arid regions under climate change, develop and apply innovative approaches and mathematical and computational modeling methods, share recent research results and practical experience, and strengthen international academic cooperation in this field.

Key Themes of the Conference:

1. Water Diplomacy and Integrated Approaches in International Relation: Interdisciplinary Approaches to Sustainable Development, Communication and Global Security

- Issues of systemic analysis in international relations and world politics in the context of water diplomacy
- Economic, environmental and energy aspects of sustainable development
- Systemic approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

2. Mathematical and computer modeling of optimal water resources management under climate change

- Optimal water resource management under climate change
- Modeling water resource dynamics and climate variability
- Methods of applied and computational mathematics in irrigation system modeling.

3. Environmental and Hydrogeological Processes in the Aral Sea Region: Analysis Based on Modern Technologies

- Analysis of hydrogeological processes in the Aral Sea region
- Application of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data technologies to environmental challenges
- Simulation and stochastic modeling of environmental and hydrogeological processes in the Aral region.

The event was conducted in a hybrid format with participation in English, Russian, and Uzbek. The conference provided a high-level platform for scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

On The Question Of Calculating The Sedimentation (Siltation) Of Backed-Up Reaches Of Low-Head Dams

Baimanov Ruslan Kenesbaevich¹, Adenbayev Asenbay Sabitovich²

¹ *Karakalpak State University, Doctor of Philosophy in Technical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor, Head of the Department of "Construction of Complex Engineering Structures"*

² *Karakalpak State University, 1st-year doctoral student*

e-mail: ruslan_kenesbaevich@list.ru¹, adenbayev@gmail.com²

Abstract

This paper examines sedimentation processes in backwater reaches of low-head hydraulic structures, focusing on the interaction between flow, channel morphology, and sediment transport. Based on existing methods (primarily those of S. T. Altunin and V. N. Sholokhov) and field data from river hydroschemes, the study analyzes the staged development of sediment deposition, changes in backwater length, and associated hydraulic conditions. Special attention is given to sandy and gravel-pebble sedimentation schemes, limiting slope formation, and long-term morphological adjustments of river channels. Case studies of the Takhiatash and Tuyamuyun hydroschemes on the Amu Darya River illustrate significant channel transformations, including backwater extension and bed aggradation. The results emphasize the importance of accurate sedimentation forecasting for ensuring the reliable operation of hydraulic structures and water intake systems.

Channel deformations caused by hydraulic structures on rivers are characterized by the extremely complex interaction between the riverbed, the flow, and the structure itself. Although studies of these processes conducted by scientists from various countries have achieved significant results, they are still insufficient.

At present, only siltation processes lend themselves to relatively complete analysis, whereas sediment deposition processes are still evaluated insufficiently. At the same time, the operation of low-head dams continues to face numerous difficulties and adverse consequences associated with channel reformation, in which sediment deposition processes are the dominant factor.

There are considerably fewer methods for predicting the sediment deposition of backed-up reaches than methods for predicting siltation. The most well-known is the method developed by S. T. Altunin [1], which was later further developed by V. N. Sholokhov [2].

The method is based on the use of data on the actual sediment deposition in a number of backwater reaches, including the well-studied Sarykurgan Hydroscheme on the Sokh River and the Gazalkent Hydroscheme on the Chirchiq River, investigated both in field conditions and on hydraulic models.

The period of sediment deposition is divided into three calculation stages. The end of the first stage is considered to be the moment when the bed load sediments reach the hydroscheme; by this time, the backwater length is assumed to be equal to 1.8–2 times the initial backwater length, which is determined by the formula

$$l_6 = H_n / i_6$$

The second period is characterized by the transport of part of the sediments into the downstream reach; its end is determined by the cessation of the general scour of the channel in the downstream reach due to the removal of part of the sediments from the upstream reach. At this moment in time, the backwater length is equal to 5.5 times the initial backwater length.

At the end of the third period, almost all the sediments will have passed through the hydroscheme cross-section, and the backwater length will be equal to 8–10 times the initial backwater length. It also follows that, according to V. N. Sholokhov, the slope in a completely sediment-filled backwater reach amounts to 7/8–9/10 of the natural channel slope.

The duration of the indicated formation periods is determined by the following relationship:

$$T = \frac{W}{\alpha_{cp} \cdot \beta_{cp} \cdot G} \quad (1)$$

where:

- T - duration of sediment deposition (years);
- W - volume of sediment deposition, thousand m³;
- G - average annual bed-load sediment discharge, thousand m³/year;
- α_{cp} - share of suspended sediments participating in the sedimentation of the backed-up reach (during the first formation period, $\alpha_{cp} = 1.0 - 2.0$; during the second and third periods, $\alpha_{cp} = 1.0$);
- β_{cp} - coefficient of sediment accumulation in the backed-up reach; during the first period all bed sediments are retained, while during the subsequent periods the retention ratio varies from 0.94 to 0.1 and depends on the proportion of water withdrawal and the characteristics of the river section where the backed-up reach is formed.

The process of sediment deposition in backed-up reaches by coarse and fine sandy sediments is physically very similar to the accumulative processes frequently observed in rivers; however, in terms of intensity, it significantly exceeds natural river processes [3, 4].

As a result of the studies carried out by S. T. Altunin and I. A. Buzunov [1], V. N. Sholokhov [2], A. M. Mukhamedov [4], and V. S. Lapshenkov [3], it was concluded that in the zone of additional backwater, the flow slope formed during sediment deposition is always smaller than the natural river slope in the same reach.

In nature, channel-forming sediments are divided into two fundamentally different sedimentation schemes: gravel–pebble deposits and sandy deposits. The process of sedimentation of upstream backwater reaches by gravel–pebble material occurs as follows [3, 4]. The accumulation of the coarsest sediments begins in the zone where the backwater curve meets the natural river water level; the finest fractions may either be immediately transported beyond the backwater reach (in the case of small backwater heads), or be deposited together with sandy fractions during the siltation process.

At the initial stage, the length of the sedimentation zone is small; later it increases, with both boundaries of the sedimentation reach shifting simultaneously: the downstream boundary moves toward the hydraulic structure, while the upstream boundary moves further upstream. As a result, the planform area of sedimentation expands, and the rate of bed aggradation decreases. Over time, a significant volume of sediment deposits accumulates within the accumulation zone in the form of channel features (islands). Therefore, sedimentation is accompanied by a considerable additional rise in water levels.

One of the main elements of the calculation is determining the location of the downstream boundary of the sedimentation reach. It is usually situated at the cross-section where siltation has almost ceased. In this case, gravel is also deposited within the zone of sand accumulation. The minimum diameter (d_{min}) of gravel particles accumulating in the sedimentation reach can be determined by the following formula.

$$d_{\text{мин}} = 25,6 Q_p^{0,30} (pw)^{0,76} \quad (2)$$

where:

- pw - sediment load of the flow in suspended form;
- Q_p - design water discharge;
- D - particle size (mm), above which gravel particles are deposited upstream of the investigated cross-section (particles smaller than this size are accumulated together with sandy fractions).

The movement of the downstream boundary of the sedimentation reach toward the hydraulic structure is governed by siltation processes: where siltation has ended, sediment deposition begins.

The estimation of sedimentation volumes is carried out based on cross-sectional areas defined at a given water level elevation by the topography of the cross-section, the silted area, and the water flow area.

To determine the cross-sectional area of the flow under natural sediment load conditions (at the downstream boundary section), the average flow depth is calculated using a formula derived from the equation of A. N. Gostunsky:

$$H = \left[\frac{3300 Q_p^3 n^p}{B^3 (pw)} \right] \quad (3)$$

The width of the flow is determined using the formula of S. T. Altunin:

$$B = (KH)^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (4)$$

In this case, for sandy deposits, ($K = 3.0$) and ($m = 0.5$) are adopted.

Then, for the same cross-section and water discharge, the flow cross-sectional area is determined under the assumption that particles with a diameter d_{min} are transported to the section.

The average depth is calculated using the formula of V. S. Lapshenkov:

$$H = \left[\frac{Q_p n^{\frac{2}{3}}}{B} \left(\frac{10}{d} \right)^{1/2} \right]^{\frac{1}{1+1/2y}} \quad (5)$$

The flow width can also be calculated using Altunin's formula.

Next, the sedimentation volume over the entire length of the additional backwater reach is determined for the specified calculation time interval:

$$V_{\text{эH}} = \frac{G_{\partial} t}{\gamma_{\partial}} \quad (6)$$

where:

- G_{∂} - annual bed-load sediment discharge participating in sediment deposition;
- γ_{∂} - their bulk (volume) density;
- T - time from the beginning of sediment accumulation up to the moment when the downstream boundary of sedimentation reaches the design cross-section.

After this, sedimentation is calculated for the upper computational reach located upstream of the first one. Again, using the grain-size distribution curve, the armorings (coarse layer) diameter at the upstream cross-section is selected, and the water surface slope within the reach, as well as the flow depth and width, are determined. Finally, the sedimentation area and volume are computed.

Let us consider the sedimentation schemes of upstream backwater reaches formed by sandy sediments (figure). In this case, sedimentation occurs through the accumulation of particles smaller than 0.05–0.1 mm. An illustrative example is the Amu Darya River. The channel-forming sediments of this river consist of fractions of 0.1–0.5 mm. In the middle and lower reaches of the

Amu Darya, the construction of the Kyzylayak Hydroscheme, Tuyamuyun Hydroscheme, and Takhiatash Hydroscheme was planned.

Scheme of sedimentation of backwater reaches by sandy deposits: 1- natural (pre-dam) water level; 2 - bed profile after siltation and sediment deposition; 3 - backwater curve after siltation and sediment deposition.

The Takhiatash Hydroscheme is located on a lowland reach of the Amu Darya River, which is characterized by a high concentration of suspended sediments and an unstable channel. The long-term average monthly turbidity ranges from 2 to 4 kg/m³, while the maximum observed discharge is 6,940 m³/s. The largest sediment particle size does not exceed 0.25 mm, with an average diameter of 0.12 mm. Bed-load sediments account for 8–10% of suspended sediments. The long-term average sediment transport (at Chatly) is 123 million tons per year. The channel slopes are relatively steep ($i = 0.00012\text{--}0.00016$), and the mean flow velocity reaches up to 2.5 m/s.

The hydroscheme was commissioned in 1974. During the periods 1974–1977, 1982–1986, and 1996–2000, field investigations were carried out by staff of SANIIRI (Central Asian Scientific Research Institute of Irrigation).

In the upstream reach, studies were conducted at 46 cross-sections over a length of 17.5 km, and in the downstream reach at 31 cross-sections over a length of 14 km [5]. The processes of siltation in the upstream reach and general channel scour in the downstream reach were investigated in order to assess the possible adverse impact of these morphological changes on water intake conditions for canals and on the operation of the hydroscheme as a whole.

Intensive morphological transformations of the upstream reach of the Takhiatash Hydroscheme continued for 10 years from the beginning of its operation. During this 10-year period, 21.67 million m³ of sediments were deposited in the upstream reach (the maximum silted volume), amounting to 48% of the total channel storage capacity formed at the normal water level (NWL) in the upstream reach. At the same time, intensive inflow of bed-load sediments and gradual aggradation of the channel bed in the downstream reach were observed.

Thus, after 1982, siltation of the upstream reach was completed and the process of sediment deposition began. The initial backwater length from the Takhiatash Hydroscheme (NWL 77.2 m) upstream was 17 km; as a result of sediment deposition by bed-load sediments, it increased to 70 km, i.e., by a factor of four.

Upstream of this hydroscheme, the Tuyamuyun Hydroscheme was commissioned in 1982. Above the Tuyamuyun gauging station, the river's suspended load contains a small amount of gravel, but its role in accumulation processes is minor; the channel-forming sediments are fractions of 0.1–0.5 mm. The initial backwater length from the Tuyamuyun Hydroscheme (NWL 130.0 m) upstream is 84 km, and during sedimentation by channel-forming sandy fractions it will reach 330 km, i.e., it will also increase by a factor of four [3].

Calculations of sedimentation under such conditions are of particular importance, since the resulting additional inundation may extend over large lengths and areas. In addition, the sediment regime near the hydroscheme and other water-intake structures in the upstream reach is of great interest.

In this scheme, the sedimentation reach increases in length over time; the movement of its downstream boundary toward the hydroscheme, as in the previous scheme, is determined through siltation calculations.

A characteristic feature of sedimentation that can be used in the computational scheme is that over a large part of the sedimentation reach, a slope close to the limiting value is established, which will persist for a very long time over the predominant length of the upstream backwater reach.

According to the exponential law describing both siltation and sedimentation processes, once 90–95% of the ultimately sedimentable volume has been deposited, the intensity of the accumulation processes sharply decreases. In this case, only about 5% of the sediments continue to settle, and these are retained for a very long time in the upstream reach, contributing to the formation of a wandering channel within the overall accumulation process. Such a nature of the process determines the values of the limiting channel slope.

The limiting slope is determined by the following formula [3]:

$$i = 0,00625 \frac{(pw)^{0,70}}{Q_p^{0,095}} \quad (7)$$

The sedimentation calculation is carried out starting from the cross-section where siltation has ended (figure, section I). Next, using formulas (3) and (4), the elements of the cross-sectional profile are determined, and based on the limiting slope i_{np} , the water level elevation and the connection between the backwater level and the natural river levels are established (figure, section 2). These parameters are sufficient to determine the sedimentation volume over a known period of sediment accumulation. This volume must be compared with the potential transport of channel-forming sediments over the same operational period.

REFERENCES

- [1] Altunin S. T. *Regulation of River Channels at Water Intakes*. Moscow: Selkhozgiz, 1956. 242 p.
- [2] Sholokhov V. N. On the formation of river channels in the reaches of low-head dams in mountainous and foothill river sections // *Proceedings of SANIIRI*. 1957. Issue 84. 38 p.
- [3] Lapshenkov V. S. *Forecasting Channel Deformations in the Reaches of River Hydroschemes*. Leningrad: Gidrometeoizdat, 1979. 238 p.
- [4] Mukhamedov A. M. *Operation of Low-Head Hydroschemes on Sediment-Transporting Rivers*. Tashkent: Fan, 1976. 238 p.
- [5] Baymanov K. I. *Flows in Deformable Open Channels*. Nukus: Karakalpakstan, 2008. 352 p.
- [6] Baymanov K. I., Baimanov R.K. *A study of the dynamics of the flow and the round process in urbanized areas of plain rivers*. IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental., 2023, 1212(1), 012006.
- [7] Baymanov K. I., Baimanov R.K. *Investigation and Calculation of Channel Deformations in the Lower Reaches of Low-Head Hydraulic Structures of Lowland Rivers*. Power Technology and Engineering., 2024, 57(5), p.p. 680–689.